

This paper investigated the dependence of the stability of the knee joint, when exposed to external rotational load on the lower leg, on the position of the graft of the tendon of the popliteal muscle. Estimation finite-element models of the right knee joint of an adult were constructed, which included the articular ends of the bones that form this joint, as well as its main ligaments. The models reflected a surgery to restore posterolateral angle structures and differed only in the position of the popliteal tendon graft. That position was set by the point of attachment of the graft to the posterior surface of the tibia. At the same time, the fixation point changed both vertically and horizontally, in the frontal plane. In addition, a control model was built in which the hamstring tendon was completely absent. As a result of the calculations, patterns of the distribution of the fields of movement of the points of the finite-element model were obtained. As criteria for assessing the effectiveness of the selected position of the graft, movements of the lower leg model in the horizontal plane were proposed. Analysis of the results of the calculations showed that the greatest movements in all directions were obtained in the control model, in which the hamstring of the popliteal muscle was absent. The magnitudes of the considered movements derived from the control model exceeded the same values in the model with minimal movements by 17, 37, 17, 32, and 16 %. From the point of view of the stability of the tibia under rotational load, the most effective was the fixation of the graft on the posterior surface of the tibia as laterally as possible and closer to its articular surface. This is indicated by the magnitude of the movements, which, in this case, turned out to be the smallest in all directions

Keywords: *knee joint, hamstring tendon, external rotational load, graft, finite-element model, stiffness characteristics*

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INFLUENCE OF THE FIXATION POINT OF THE ARTIFICIAL POPLITEAL MUSCLE GRAFT ON THE STABILITY OF THE KNEE JOINT UNDER EXTERNAL ROTATIONAL LOAD

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1. Introduction

The knee joint is one of the most important and largest joints in the human body. Owing to it, people can perform a variety of movements of the lower limb. Such movements primarily include bringing the lower leg to the thigh and its removal – flexion and extension of the knee, which occur in the sagittal plane, as well as internal and external rotation – in the horizontal.

The variety of movements in the knee joint is due, first of all, to its structure, which is very sophisticated as it is a whole complex of a large number of ligaments, muscles, nerves, blood vessels, cartilage, and bones. Of course, each of these elements is important for the normal functioning of the knee joint. However, special mention should be made

of the ligamentous apparatus of the joint in question, which enables the stability of the position of the bones that form the knee, under the loads acting on it. For example, the most important ligaments of the knee joint – these are the anterior and posterior cruciate ligaments, are necessary to enable the anterior and posterior stability of the specified joint, as well as for its stability under rotational load.

It should be noted here that the combined effect of body weight and the movement carried out expose the knee joint to a significant load in the form of stretching, compression, and twisting. At the same time, in young people leading an active lifestyle and athletes, the efforts arising in the ligaments increase significantly, which leads to various damages to the ligamentous apparatus from overstretching to a complete rupture. The causes of ligament damage are high-ener-

gy mechanisms of injury, such as overextension of the lower leg, twisting along the axis, excessive withdrawal, bringing the lower leg, or direct exposure to a traumatic force on the lower leg. Therefore, traumatic damage to the ligamentous apparatus of the knee joint is one of the most common, after the ankle joint and foot, primarily among the young population and athletes.

Given the above, one can argue that the study of methods for restoring the ligamentous apparatus of the knee joint is a relevant task.

2. Literature review and problem statement

Damage to the posterolateral angle of the knee joint is a significant part of the injuries to the ligamentous apparatus of this joint. Work [1] indicates that such an injury is both isolated and can be combined with ruptures of the posterior or anterior cruciate ligaments. Actually, the work considers the description of the anatomy of the ligaments of the posterolateral angle and its biomechanics. Paper [2] states that damage to the posterolateral angle of the knee joint leads to chronic lateral and external rotational instability. In addition, it is emphasized that such injuries are often combined with injuries to the posterior cruciate ligament.

A large number of scientific studies tackle the development and research of various methods for restoring the stability of the knee joint [3–5]. For example, [4] considers a technique of restoring the ligamentous apparatus, with combined injuries to the knee joint but only the posterior cruciate ligament is reconstructed. At the same time, work [3] indicates that when restoring the stability of the knee joint, insufficient attention is paid to the structures of the posterolateral angle. This, in turn, leads to unsatisfactory treatment results. This fact is also pointed out in study [6], which states that further expansion of knowledge about the anatomy and biomechanics of the posterolateral angle leads to improved diagnostic capabilities and successful treatment of knee instability.

To date, there are various techniques for restoring the posterolateral angle. However, not many studies have been reported in the literature related to the quantitative or qualitative assessment of factors affecting the results of treatment of knee instability in case of hamstring damage. Such work is necessary to determine the most effective methods for restoring the ligamentous apparatus of the knee joint. One of the few studies in which the results of treatment of instability of the knee joint are compared are [5, 7]. Thus, paper [7] compares the results obtained by only two methods: Arciero and LaPrade. And in [5], a study is performed to determine the optimal position of the damaged ligamentous structures of the knee joint during their recovery. However, the cited study is performed on cadaveric samples, which does not give a full opportunity to take into consideration the actual conditions of loading the joint.

It should be noted here that there are practically no papers in which the analysis of factors affecting the results of treatment of instability of the knee joint during rotational load, as well as the degree of influence of these factors, is reported. Thus, it can be concluded that in most of the works related to the considered area of research, data obtained on the basis of the results of surgical treatment of instability of the knee joint, or the results of experiments on cadaveric samples, are given. However, it is obvious that the use of such

approaches to assess the effectiveness of a particular method of treatment is time-consuming. In addition, they do not make it possible to fully identify the patterns of influence of certain factors on the stability of the joint in question.

The use of modern computer technology will make it possible to perform a detailed analysis of the parameters affecting the results of the treatment of damage to the ligamentous apparatus of the knee joint. In addition, based on studies of numerical models of the knee joint, it is possible to develop recommendations for the introduction of new methods for restoring the stability of this joint. An example of successful use of this approach is work [8], in which the assessment of the forces arising in the anterior cruciate ligament when the angle of inclination of the tibial plateau changes is given.

From [9], it follows that one of the main structures of the posterolateral angle of the knee joint, which enables its stability, is the tendon of the popliteal muscle. The course of surgical intervention on the plastic of this tendon involves drilling a channel in the outer condyle of the tibia from front to back. The channel exit point on the posterior surface of the tibia is the geometric location of the graft attachment. Obviously, the position of fixation of such a transplant depends on the result of treatment to restore the stability of the knee joint. However, exact recommendations for its choice in the literature have not been found. That is, the unsolved issue is to determine the optimal position of the attachment point of the graft of the hamstring tendon muscle while restoring the stability of the knee joint, which is proposed to be solved in the current study.

3. The aim and objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to determine the optimal position of fixation of the tendon graft on the posterior surface of the tibia during external rotation of the tibia. This will make it possible to enable the necessary stability of the knee joint when performing an operation to restore the functions of the popliteal muscle.

To accomplish the aim, the following tasks have been set:

- to determine the magnitude of movements that occur in the knee joint during rotational load;
- to investigate the nature of the distribution of displacement fields arising in the elements of the knee joint model.

4. The study materials and methods

The object of this study was the knee joint and its ligamentous apparatus.

The main hypothesis of the study assumes that the position of the graft of the tendon of the popliteal muscle affects the stability of the knee joint during rotational load.

The study was carried out using a software package based on the finite-element method in the ANSYS software environment (USA). In order to simplify the calculations, the geometric model consisted only of the articular ends of the tibia, fibula, and femur bones that form the knee joint (Fig. 1).

Given the complex geometry of the bone surface, the articular ends were built from computed tomography (CT) data of the knee joint of an adult, using specialized software for processing CT images (3D Slicer). The resulting model

in the format “stl” was used for further calculations. Consequently, the shape and size of the model corresponded to the actual knee joint of a person. At the same time, the overall (maximum) dimensions of the model in the horizontal plane were 100*70 mm. In order to reduce the total number of finite elements, the model was limited in height to 15 cm.

Fig. 1. Three-dimensional model of the knee joint: *a* – rear view; *b* – view from the outside; *c* – front view; *d* – view from the inside

It should be noted that in this study, the estimation model of the knee joint corresponded to the position of extension in its vertical orientation.

When modeling the stability of the knee joint, it is quite difficult to fully reflect its structure and the behavior of individual ligaments, both from a geometric and physical point of view. Each ligament consists of fibers that form individual branches, which, in turn, are attached to the articular ends of the bones at several points, occupying some area on the surface of the bone. In this case, the ligament along its length can vary in thickness, expanding to the places of attachment, and due to the different directions of the fibers to have a rotation of the cross-section around the longitudinal axis of the ligament, that is, “twisting”. In addition, the ligaments have not only elastic physical and mechanical properties but also such as creep and relaxation, determining of and accounting for which is a laborious task.

Obviously, taking into consideration the structural features and properties of the ligaments would lead to a significant increase in the time for building a model (the geometric aspect of the problem) and for performing the calculation (the physical aspect of the problem), and often it is impossible at all.

Taking into consideration the above, the ligament was considered as an element, in terms of the resistance of materials, which works only on stretching, that is, only longitudinal tensile forces can occur in it. Therefore, it was proposed to replace the actual shapes of the ligaments with cylindrical elements with low bending stiffness (by reducing the size of the cylinder diameter). The bases of the cylinders were fixed in the places of the beginning of the ligaments, which were defined as the center of the contact area of the ligament with the surface of the bone. The diameters of all cylinders were equal to 2 mm, and the lengths were due to the places of attachment of the ligaments (Fig. 2).

Table 1 gives the actual dimensions of the cross-sections and the length of the ligaments of the knee joint.

Regarding the physical and mechanical properties of the elements of the model (bones and ligaments of the knee joint), we note the following. The material of the elements was supposed to be elastic, homogeneous, and isotropic. Note that the subject of this study is primarily the behavior of the ligamen-

tous apparatus of the knee joint when it is loaded. Therefore, given the significant difference in the elastic properties of bone tissue and ligaments, the articular ends of the bones, in the entire volume, were given the properties of cortical bone tissue (spongy tissue was not separated). In the calculations, the following values were accepted: the Young modulus of bone tissue – $2 \cdot 10^4$ MPa, Poisson coefficient – 0.25 [15]. The mechanical values of the ligamentous apparatus used in the calculations, which correspond to the average values of the properties of the ligaments of the knee joint of an adult, are given in Table 2.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the location of the ligaments of the knee joint: *a* – rear view; *b* – view from the outside; *c* – front view; *d* – view from the inside

Note that the replacement of the anatomical shape of the ligaments with their simplified models in the form of cylinders leads to a change in the stiffness characteristics of the models:

- EA is the cross-sectional stiffness of the rod (ligament) during stretching;
- E is the Young modulus;
- A is the cross-sectional area.

Table 1

Size of the ligaments of the knee joint [10–14]

Ligament	Length, mm	Cross-sectional area, mm ²
Anterior cruciate ligament	32	37.4
Posterior cruciate ligament	35	64.05
Lateral collateral ligament	48.15	8.76
medial collateral ligament	68.99	24.54
Hamstring tendon	34.3	21.9

Table 2

Elastic properties of the ligaments of the knee joint [11, 14, 16]

Ligament	Young modulus, MPa	Poisson coefficient	Reduced Young modulus, MPa
Anterior cruciate ligament	123	0.4	1464
Posterior cruciate ligament	168	0.4	3425
Lateral collateral ligament	280	0.4	781
Medial collateral ligament	224	0.4	1750
Hamstring tendon	130.9	0.4	913

In this case, it becomes necessary to determine such moduli of elasticity, the value of which, taking into consideration the size of the cross-sections of the models of ligaments, would give the models of ligaments stiffness values similar to the actual ones. For this purpose, the calculation of the reduced modulus of elasticity of the ligaments was performed, based on the equality of the stiffness values for the sprain of the ligament and the cylinder modeling it, that is

$$E_l A_l = E_c A_c,$$

$E_l A_l$ is the stiffness of the ligament for stretching, $E_c A_c$ is the stiffness of the cylinder for stretching.

Hence, the reduced modulus of elasticity of the ligament:

$$E_c = E_l A_l / A_c.$$

The results of these calculations are given above in Table 2.

The technique of setting the load was determined as follows. As is known [17], on the side of the lower leg, the knee joint is formed by the articular ends of two bones: the tibia and the fibula, which are present in the estimation model. These bones can be mobile relative to each other, and in the case of applying a load to the lower leg, the effect on both bones is transmitted simultaneously. In order to exclude their mutual displacement, the articular ends at the bottom of the model were rigidly connected to each other by a cylindrical element (platform), 10 mm high, and 120 mm in diameter (Fig. 3, *a, b, d*). The mechanical properties of the platform corresponded to those of the cortical bone. In addition, at the top of the tibia model, the tibia and fibula were connected by a cylindrical element with a diameter of 10 mm and the mechanical properties of the hamstring of the popliteal muscle (Fig. 3, *b, c*).

The present study is based on the evaluation of one of the functions of the popliteal muscle – ensuring the stability of the lower leg during external rotation of the lower leg. Therefore, the loading of the model was carried out by torque, which was applied to the lower base of the cylindrical platform in the direction of the outside (Fig. 3, *d*). In other words, we performed an external rotation of the tibia. The magnitude of the torque was chosen arbitrarily and, after preliminary calculations, it was determined at the level of 15 N*m.

Regarding boundary conditions, note the following. In the actual knee joint, contact interaction takes place between the femur and tibia. In this case, contact is realized through such joint structures as cartilage and menisci. The presence of these structures in the joint gap indicates that there is no direct contact between the bones, and there is a certain distance directly between the articular surface of the femur and tibia. Obviously, the presence and consideration of these structures of the joint can lead to an increase in its stiffness during rotational load, primarily due to the occurrence of frictional forces. However, it should be noted here that the contacting surfaces of the knee joint are congruent and smooth, which leads to a decrease in the friction force in it, and in addition, synovial fluid is present in the joint bag itself, which also reduces the level of friction in the joint. Due to these features of the joint under study, we can say that friction on the contacting articular surfaces is practically absent and can be ignored when performing calculations.

Thus, for the study, boundary conditions of the calculation model were proposed, which reflected the presence of a distance between the articular surfaces of the femur and tibia and simulated the absence of friction in the joint. It was forbidden to move the fragment of the femur in all directions. For the model of the lower leg, vertical movement was prohibited, in other directions, free displacements were allowed.

For ease of orientation, a rectangular coordinate system was introduced (Fig. 3, *a*). With respect to the model, the *x*-axis was directed from the inside out; *y*-axis – perpendicular to the *x*-axis, rear forward; the *z*-axis is perpendicular to the *xOy* plane, from bottom to top. That is, the *z*-axis coincided with the vertical axis of the lower limb model, and the *xOy* plane was perpendicular to this axis.

To perform a study to determine the most optimal position of fixation of the popliteal muscle graft on the posterior surface of the tibia, 9 estimation schemes were constructed, which differed in the place of its attachment. Control model 10 was also built, in which the hamstring tendon was missing. The graft was modeled with a circular cylinder with a diameter of 2 mm. The upper edge of the graft was attached to the anatomical point of the beginning of the hamstring on the outer condyle of the femur, and the point of its fixation on the tibia changed vertically and horizontally. For the convenience of orientation of the lower part of the graft on the tibia, its connection was carried out through cylindrical elements created on the posterior surface of the outer condyle, which set the position of attachment of the graft to the tibia (Fig. 4, *a, b*).

Fig. 3. Model of the knee joint: *a* – coordinate system used; *b, c* – the connection of the tibia and fibula in the proximal epiphysis; *d* – direction of application of rotational load to the platform

Fig. 4. Scheme of the location of the graft fixation points for the reconstruction of the hamstring of the popliteal muscle (rear view): *a* – general view of the tibia from behind; *b* – designation of graft fixation points